

ETHNICS

ABOUT AI AND DATA

In education and lifelong learning

CASE

TRAINING MANAGEMENT

A director of a vocational training institute understands that, when working with at-risk students, it is very important to create a continuous track of learning and behavior data. A system based on Amazon Cloud Services and a private American company is purchased that a) combine data from the Italian electronic register; b) creates an emotion recognition based on facial tracking; c) generates analytics (statistical summary graphs) that allow understanding which students are at risk. The system has a predictive algorithm that sends recommendations to teachers on the status of students; furthermore, the director is able to collect expressions of involvement or boredom during teachers' activities, being able to track teacher effectiveness. One teacher is called out in particular because apparently there are many problematic cases in her class. It turns out that there is a fault in the facial tracking system and it is not giving appropriate indications.

Have you ever found yourself in a similar situation?

What are your feelings about this?

Let us consider the following ethical criteria

#CARD II - TRASPARENZA

#CARD VII - ACCOUNTABILITY

What are the problems in this practice?

What would be an “ethical” approach?

Future of Educational Professionalism: Your Reflections

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